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Corporate tax avoidance, Earnings management and Earnings manipulation in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study applies broad approach to analyse the impact of corporate tax avoidance on earnings manipulation in Nigeria. Added to that, the study also investigates whether earnings management plays any moderating role in the relationship between corporate tax avoidance on earnings manipulation. The study uses unbalanced panel data of 116 quoted companies in Nigeria from the period 2009 to 2016. The linear dynamic panel models designed for the study were estimated using one-step different Generalised Method of Moment (GMM) technique. The main findings are in two folds. First, the study indicates that the impact of corporate tax avoidance is positive and statistically significant on earnings manipulation. Secondly, the study provides evidence which suggests that earnings management significantly moderated the relationship between corporate tax avoidance and earnings manipulation. Unlike previous studies which investigated the effect of corporate tax avoidance on earnings manipulation using a single tax factor, this study is novel in applying corporate tax avoidance to estimate the impact of tax aggressiveness on earnings manipulation. Furthermore, the study also fills knowledge gap in the literature by providing new evidence indicating that earnings management plays significant role in the relationship between corporate tax avoidance and earnings manipulation.

Keywords: corporate tax avoidance, earnings management, earnings manipulation, GMM, Nigeria cashETR, tax savings.

1.0 Introduction

The reaction of avoidance on earnings manipulation has emerged issue of interest to analyst, investors, managers and other market participants (Lipe 1990; Chan, Jegadeesh, and Lakonishok, 2006; and Cahan, Emmanuel, and Sun, 2009). Managers are much concerned about meeting analyst forecast by maintaining sustainable growth of the companies as means to protect themselves, while researchers have documented issues, where companies with higher earnings having lower effective tax rate is an issue of companies tax avoidance practices. Beneish (1999) stated that earnings manipulation occurs when company's managers violate generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP) to favourably represent the company's financial performance. From the previous studies perspectives' researchers has documented the effect of tax avoidance on earnings manipulation such as Lyimo (2014); Atwood, Michael, Drake, Linda and Myers (2010) concluded that higher consistency between accounting profits and tax base earnings adds to the quality of earnings and undermines earnings persistence; Linda and Chen (2012) indicated that the reaction of tax policies on earnings management is significant and it affects information content of earnings quality as well., Mohammadreza, Aliasghar and Hamid (2013). Their results show differences on how investors react to issues of avoidance on earnings manipulation on different environment. None of these studies factored current Nigerian situation considering tax agency strategies and stakeholders reaction of avoidance on earnings manipulation of Nigerian firms to the best of researcher's knowledge.

In Nigeria context, as the Federal Inland Revenue Services focus on improving compliance and expanding the tax base rather than introducing new taxes or increasing the rates of existing taxes due to decline in oil revenue (PWC Nigeria tax alert September 2015). Nigeria is undergoing a lot of restructuring on fiscal policy such as National tax policy, transfer pricing guidelines for multinational enterprises and tax administrations which mandate all organizations to include transfer pricing declaration and disclosure form during tax return with effective from January 2017 (Nolands taxflash 2017) , Voluntary assets and income declaration scheme (VAIDS) and so on. One of the Federal Inland Revenue Services strategy is evaluating tax avoidance practices of Nigeria firms against their earnings. As tax agencies are on the pressure of increasing government revenue through taxation, this has created another face for valuing firms' earnings through tax avoidance practice. These agencies have increased its drive on tax audit and investigations on Nigeria firms publishing reports on firm's tax avoidance strategies, by using their statutory tax rate and effective tax rate. This recent process will lead to another reaction to Nigeria firms by stakeholders ranging from government, intending investors, business managers, stock market analyst and business owners, which is the motivating factor of this research trying to find out the reaction of tax avoidance practices on earnings manipulation on the quoted firms in Nigeria. What are the tax avoidance reactions to firms' earnings manipulation? Is it significant? To what extent of significance? Is it positive or negative? To address these gaps in the corporate tax avoidance and earnings management on earnings manipulation literature, a sample of 165 quoted firms in Nigeria stock exchange from 2009 to 2016 is used. The variables of interest are Beneish's earnings manipulation model (a measure of earnings manipulation), modified Jones earnings management model (a proxy for of earnings management), cash effective tax rate, long term cash effective tax rate, tax savings, book tax gap, temporary tax difference and permanent tax difference (as tax avoidance indicators). This study attempts to answer two questions: (1) Does corporate tax avoidance and earnings management adoption significantly affects earnings manipulation in Nigeria? (2) Is the interaction of corporate tax avoidance and earnings management adoption significantly affects earnings manipulation in Nigeria? The empirical investigation employs pooled, panel regression with fixed and random effect panel data regression and dynamic one-step difference generalized method of moments technique. Our findings, for the most part, align with previous studies. The rest of the paper is structured as Section 2 briefly reviews empirical literature on earnings manipulation. It discusses its effect on tax avoidance. The research design is described in Section 3, while Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings. Section 5 provides a summary of the results, conclusion and recommendations.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Studies on developed markets

Dyreg et al., (2010), focused on long run corporate tax avoidance on earning using United States. They used accounting effective tax rate as measure tax avoidance. The result indicates a positive significant effect of accounting effective tax rate on firms earning as investors based on after-tax results to assess firms earning. Similarly, Armstrong, Blouin and Larcker (2012) studied the effects of incentives for tax planning on firms earnings. They used accounting effective tax rate to measure tax avoidance to see the effects of tax avoidance on firms earning using regression analysis on firms quoted in United States. Their result indicates a positive significant effect of accounting effective tax rate on firms earning.

Huseynov and Klamm (2012) worked on the e tax avoidance, tax management and corporate social responsibility. They used S&P 500 firms in United states (number of firms varies between 25 and 425 per

year and depends upon the availability of data). They reported that accounting effective tax rate has been a widely used measure of tax avoidance because it measures tax avoidance relative to accounting earnings. Their result stated a positive significant effect of accounting effective tax rate on corporate social responsibility indicating higher firms earnings.

Desai and Dharmapala (2006) worked on corporate tax avoidance on firm value using United States firms. They argue that aggressive tax planning reducing tax may not necessarily be beneficial to stockholders and earnings. They used regression analysis to analyze the effect accounting effective tax rate on firms' earnings. Their result shows positive significant effect of accounting effective tax rate on firms' earnings. They are of the simple view of corporate tax avoidance as a transfer of resources from the state to shareholders is incomplete given the agency problems characterizing shareholder-manager relations as it negatively affect firms earning.

Hope, Ma and Thomas (2012) focused on tax avoidance and geographic earnings disclosure. They employed current effective tax rate to measure tax avoidance while examining the association between corporate tax avoidance and geographical earnings' disclosure practices using United States multinationals. They found positive significant effect of current effective tax rate on geographic firms earning disclosures. Similarly, Lanis & Richardson (2012) worked on effect of tax avoidance on corporate social responsibility. They used regression analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables using 408 Australian firms. They measured tax avoidance using current effective tax rate on corporate social responsibility. Their result shows positive significant effect of current effective tax rate on corporate social responsibility indicating high tax rate which indicates high earnings quality.

Deméré, Lisowsky, Li, and Snyder, (2017) worked on the whether smoothing activities indicate higher or lower financial reporting quality drawing evidence from effective tax rates. The study used 35,201 firm year observations in United States from excluding financial, insurance and utility firms from 1996 to 2012. They used general accepted accounting principles effective tax rate, cash effective tax rate as proxy to effective tax rate including control variables as profitability, size, market-to-book, leverage, research and development expense, net operating loss carry forwards, foreign income-producing activity, intangible assets, mergers and acquisitions, capital intensity, cash holdings and losses. They used ordinary least square regression to analyse the dependent and independent variables. Their result shows a negative significant effect of effective tax rate on discretionary accruals, meaning effective tax rate serves as an indicator to financial reporting quality on both reducing and increasing firms earning.

Ayers et al (2009) worked on taxable income as a performance measure. The effects of tax planning and firms' earnings using United States firms. They used long-term cash effective tax rate to measure firms' tax avoidance. The study reported that taxable income becomes less informative for high tax avoidance firms and more informative for firms with low earnings quality suggesting that investors, at least in part, are able to distinguish sources of book-tax differences, after using regression analysis to analyse the effect. The result shows negative significant effect of long-term cash effective tax rate on firms earnings, meaning that taxation is evidence of low earning quality.

Hanlon and Slemrod (2008) focused on what does tax avoidance signal on firms earning, using stock price reactions news about tax avoidance involvement on United State quoted firms. They used regression analysis to analyze the effect of tax avoidance signal on firms earning, calculating long- term effective tax rate by the cash taxes paid summed over the two years divided by pre-tax income summed over the two

years. The result shows a negative significant effect of tax avoidance signal on firms earning, meaning that firms stock price declines when there is news about its involvement in tax avoidance. The reaction is less negative for firms that are viewed to be generally less tax aggressive.

Hanlon (2005) worked on the effects of tax avoidance on earnings management using United State large firms. The study used regression analysis to analyse long-run cash effective tax rate on persistence and accruals of large firms. The result shows negative effect of tax avoidance on earnings management, stating that large tax avoidance, on average, are systematically associated with the quality (persistence, growth) of firm earnings.

Dhaliwal et al. (2011) worked on the effect of corporate tax avoidance on firms' valuation using regression analysis to analyse long-run cash effective tax rate on firm's valuation of United State firms. Their result shows negative effects of tax avoidance on firms valuation but only for firms with weak corporate governance structures. As Frank *et al* (2009) focused on tax reporting aggressiveness on its relation to financial reporting of firm's earnings. Their result shows negative effects of tax aggressive policy on financial reporting. They reported that tax aggressive policy reduces firms earnings of sample firms.

Brad, Sharon and Sonja (2010) worked on how tax avoidance of firms influence firms earning using United State private equity ownership on portfolio firms. They examine whether private equity firms influence the extent and types of tax aggressiveness at portfolio firms as an additional source of economic value taking tax saving; cash effective tax rate; book-tax gap as independent variables on firms earning as dependent variable. The result shows negative significant effect of tax savings on earnings of the private equity ownership firms. They reported that private equity backed firms pay 14.2 percent less income tax per dollar of adjusted pre-tax income than non-private equity backed private firms, even after controlling for the presence of net operating loss and debt tax shields, which affect firms earning.

Thomas and Zhang (2010) worked on the effects of tax avoidance as contains information about core profitability that is incremental to reported earnings and information not reflected in stock prices because tax disclosures are complex and opaque. They analyzed the independent and dependent variables as tax savings, price momentum, discretionary accruals, size, book-to-market, ratio of tax income to earnings, income effect of changes in effective tax rates using regression analysis to analyzed the sample United states firms. Their result shows positive significant effects of tax savings on level of firms' earnings. They state that higher tax expense is good news for investors, as the fact that higher tax implies higher earnings. They posit that tax disclosures are not easily discovered and investors do not fully appreciate these implications for future earnings and tax expense.

Ftouhi, Ayed, and Zemzem, (2016) examined whether corporate tax planning behavior increases firm value of European countries. They used regression analysis to analyze the effect of tax savings on firm earnings. They reported the impact of tax planning on firm earnings is a function of tax savings in disclosures of tax reduction in the financial statements. They argue that tax savings affects firms value negatively due to higher agency costs. The result show that the corporate effective tax rate are below the statutory tax rate of the listed firm meaning that tax taxpayers use tax saving policies to reduce tax liability in obtaining the tax saving benefits while expose to risk related to inspection or investigation by tax authorities.

Hafkenscheid and Janssen (2009) worked on the whether income tax savings policies creates firms earnings using content analysis of theories of tax planning. The study was in Netherland. They argue that tax

planning strategies do create company value, that the value created by tax saving should be calculated separately from the value created by growth of the operating profits. Their result shows that many investors and analysts said they disregard tax as a value driver because they lack the relevant information, that firms generally are reluctant to provide information on their tax position, often arguing that this would negatively affect their position toward the taxing authorities.

Guenther, Hu, and Williams (2013) worked on the large book-tax gap effects on discretionary accruals using United States firms. They study used pre-tax book income for year, deferred tax expense for year, tax book gap as measure to tax avoidance on discretionary accrual as measure to firms earning of the firms using regression analysis to analyze the variables. Their result shows positive significant effects of tax book gap on firms' earnings while stating that large book tax gap will provide helpful information on discretionary accruals or firms earnings to investors and tax authorities.

Blaylock, Gaertner, and Shevlin, (2012) worked on the association between book-tax conformity and earnings management to determine whether managing earning upward lead to high tax and managing tax downwards leads to lower firms earnings. They used panel regression on 141,389 firm year observations across 35 countries over the period 1996-2007 on current tax expense, ratio of foreign pre-tax income to total tax expense, dividend as independent variables on accrual quality as measure of firms' earnings. The result shows a positive significant effect of book tax conformity on firms' earnings meaning that high book tax conformity indicates high earnings management which is a signal of low firms' earnings.

Diehl, (2010) worked on the ratio of deferred tax liabilities to shares as a predictor of stock prices using 3,016 United States companies. The study how investors review tax aggressive planning that are free from managerial discretion. They used regression analysis to analyse basic earnings per share, earnings per share, book value per share, deferred tax liabilities per share, retained earnings per share, market capitalization and number of shares as dependent and independent variables. Their result show statistical significant effect of tax aggressive planning on firms earnings, indicating that low firms earnings prediction errors are more positive where large book-to-tax gap exist.

Boise, (2005) worked on tax fraud and inflated corporate earnings. Whether is an alternative to the missing legislative fix, using United States firms with special emphasis on World Com corporation. The study used content analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables. The result show a significant effect of tax fraud on quality of firms earning while identifying two indicators as signal of tax fraud and inflated corporate earnings. Large book tax gap indicates lower firms' earnings and tax payment on artificial earnings to hit analysts expected target to maintain the price of the stock.

Seidman (2008) investigated the book tax income gap with factors that affect the gap and details regarding its most significant component. They study used United States firms within 1993 to 2004 while the dependent and independent are accounting rules, earnings management behavior, tax law, tax sheltering behavior, and general business conditions. The study later disaggregate book tax gap into temporary tax differences and permanent tax differences. They study use regression analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables. Temporary tax differences captures change in the net deferred tax asset or liability while permanent tax differences is statutory rate and of reconciling items not due to federal permanent differences less the total tax provision. The results show that temporary tax differences has a significant effect on firms earning with high R^2 , indicating wide variations in permanent tax difference. It reported that

tax avoidance are more significant through permanent tax differences than through temporary tax differences, stating that tax shelter create permanent tax differences. The study disagrees with previous studies that belief that tax shelter was primary cause of the rise in the book-tax income gap.

Evers, Meier and Nicolay (2016) worked on the implications of book-tax gap from a meta-analysis point on whether increased book-tax gap actually reduces firms' earnings. The study uses these variables book-tax conformity, book-tax gap, tax avoidance, and earnings management to analyze the dependent and independent variables in United States. The meta-analysis is to quantify the impact of these sources of heterogeneity in study design with respect to the sign and statistical significance of the association between tax book gap on earnings management, using meta regression analysis as an innovative tool in the empirical accounting literature to clarify the interpretation of opposing outcomes and providing guidelines for future studies. Their results show a negative effect of tax book gap on earnings management, which means higher tax book gap affects firms' earnings.

Abdul Wahab and Holland (2014) worked on the persistence of book-tax gap using non-financial quoted firm in United Kingdom from 2005 to 2010. They used effective tax rate, book tax gap, earning management, current tax expense and deferred tax as dependent and independent variables while using regression analysis to analyse the effect of the variables. Their results show a significant positive effect of tax book gap on firms earnings suggesting that taxation is a motivating factor. They reported that majority of companies' face a lower overseas statutory rate compared to the United Kingdom rate, the ability to maintain the book tax gap effect over time is consistent with an underlying tax motivation, which affects firms' earnings.

Blackburne, and Blouin, (2016) worked on the understanding the informativeness of book-tax gap using 19,129 firm year observation on listed firms in United States from 2001 to 2012. The study used book tax gap, ratio of deferred tax expense grossed up by the top statutory tax rate to average total assets, temporary and permanent different, as independent variables on discretionary accruals as proxy to firms earnings manipulation. They used counterfactual tests, simulation analyses and multiple regression analysis to analyse the dependent and independent variable. The result show a significant effect of book tax gap on firms earnings indicating that managers manipulate book income and taxable income reports due to incentives such value relevance of the report and tax reduction.

Romanus (2007) worked on the impact of firms' earnings on investors and analysts' reactions to restatement announcements with major focus using temporary tax different against firms' earnings. The study used earnings quality, restatements, book-tax differences, accruals as dependent and independent variables, analyzing cross-sectional data of 719 publicly traded firms that announced restatements between 1997 and 2004 in United States. The study reported that log of the absolute value of the total tax difference is used because both large positive and large negative tax difference provide indications of low firms earnings as reported by Hanlon and Krishnan 2005 in Romanus 2007. The result shows that temporary tax differences have negative significant effect on firms earning, which indicates that large book tax difference have lesser negative effect on market reaction on firms earnings. However, temporary tax difference conveys information of quality of earnings to investors. Temporary tax different further provides signal to investors that earnings manipulation may be problematic, thereby increasing investors' due diligence while suggesting that tax avoidance has consequences that extend beyond line outcomes.

Raedy, Seidman and Shackelford (2010) worked on book-tax differences as it matter to equity investors using 250 United States from 1993 to 2007. The study used employee benefits, environmental costs, general business expenses, differences related to foreign income, intangible property differences, inventory differences, leased property differences, differences arising from mergers, acquisitions, divestitures or restructuring, net loss carry forwards, differences related to owned tangible property, items unique to the regulated industries, differences in revenue recognition, state and local taxable income differences, differences related to subsidiaries to capture measures for temporary tax difference on firms earning as dependent variable. However, they used regression analysis to analyze the impact of the variables. Their result shows a positive significant effect on temporary tax difference on firms earnings, which is consistent as the investors favorably view increase and decrease in temporary tax difference. They reported that firms' tax obligations potentially shed information about quality of firms' earnings. They further states that investors examine temporary tax difference arising from accounts where managers enjoy right to choose in the recognition of income and expenses in respect to accrual quality of firms.

Blaylock, Shevlin and Wilson (2010) worked on tax avoidance, large positive book-tax differences, and earnings persistence, which investigate why temporary tax differences appear to serve as a useful signal of earnings persistence. Their analysis focuses on firms with large temporary tax differences because these differences could be a signal of either earnings management or tax avoidance on 21,205 United States firm year observations. They used pre-tax book income, pre-tax book income for the current year divided by average asset, modified jones model discretionary accruals, cash effective tax rate, temporary tax differences, earnings management to analyze the dependent and independent variables while analyzing the effects with regression analysis. Their result shows a positive significant effect on temporary tax difference on firms' earnings stating that temporary tax differences serve as a useful signal of future earnings, which some cases lead to lower earnings. They reported that despite concerns over the limited information provided to investors in respect to differences between a firm's book and taxable income, they find that investors are able to use the disclosures to look through to the source of temporary tax differences and ascertain firms' earnings.

Deslandes and Landary (2007) worked on taxable income, tax-book difference and earnings manipulation. They investigated how taxable income, temporary tax difference effects assessing earnings manipulation, while stating that is somehow for a firm to report high earnings as sometimes pays little tax. They reported that gap between temporary tax differences and reported earnings might be indication of financial statement manipulations, and tax avoidance behaviour. They used all firms listed at Toronto stock exchange Canada for the period of 2000 to 2005, while the variables are earning before taxes, taxable income, total tax differences, temporary tax differences, permanent tax differences, cash flow from operations. Regression analysis used to analyse the impact of the independent on the dependent variables. Their result show a positive significant effect of temporary tax differences on earning manipulation, stating that temporary tax difference helps predicting firms' future earnings.

Lev and Nissim (2004) worked on taxable income, future earnings, and equity values. They ascertain the ability of a tax based fundamental to predict earnings growth and stock returns. The tax fundamental reflects temporary and permanent tax differences as well as tax accruals such as changes in the tax valuation allowance. They used taxable income; deferred taxes; temporary and permanent tax differences, earnings manipulation; cash flow from operations, earnings management; market efficiency to analyze the dependent and independent variable with regression analysis. The study used a sample of 40,372 United States firm

year observations on 5,384 different firms for 28 years ranging from 1973 to 2000, gotten from Compustat database. Their result show a negative significant effect of temporary tax differences on earning manipulation, it suggest that permanent tax differences and temporary tax difference are relevant as deferred taxes for predicting earnings growth. They reported that decrease in the tax and increase cash flow from operations coefficients appears consistent with a general deterioration in the quality of earnings during the late 1980s and 1990s. According to Lev and Zarowin 1999 in Lev and Nissim 2004, reflecting the increasing importance of permanent tax differences and temporary tax difference indicators in predicting earnings manipulation. However, they reported that the existence of permanent book-tax differences does not change taxable income and tax relative to book income. While permanent differences may either, strengthen or weaken the information in taxable income less reported earnings, depending on their variability and correlations. The study supported Dhaliwal et al. 2002 in Lev and Nissim 2000, which document that changes in the effective tax rate, which are due to permanent differences and tax accruals, have negative effects on firms' incentives to increase reported earnings.

Studies on emerging markets

Salihu et al., (2013) worked on the measures of corporate tax avoidance, empirical evidence from an emerging economy Malaysia. They use long-run cash effective tax rate as the proportion of cash taxes paid to the accounting income before tax, accounting effective tax rate and current effective tax rate as measure to tax avoidance. They used regression analysis to determine the effects of tax avoidance on firms' earnings. Their result shows negative significant effect of current and long-run cash effective tax rate on firms earning, suggesting that the relative information content of taxable income for low earnings firms increased concerns of opportunistic earnings management.

Chen and Chu (2005) worked on a model of tax avoidance on internal control and external manipulation using Malaysia firms. They employed current effective tax rate to measure tax avoidance. They argued that tax avoidance leads to loss of internal control in case the managers act selfishly given the incomplete nature that affects firms earning. The result shows positive significant effect of tax avoidance on internal control that affects firms' earnings. Consistent with Adhikari, Derashid and Zhang (2005) on effect of effective tax rate on firms earning using from Malaysia firms.

Amidu, Yorke, and Harvey, (2016) worked on the effects of financial reporting standards on tax avoidance and firms earnings. The study employ a sample of 116 firms listed in Ghana stock exchange. The study used effective tax rate, statutory tax rate and book tax gap as a measure to tax avoidance while Modified Jones model of earnings management as measure to earnings manipulation. They used multiple regressive analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables. The result show significant effect on tax avoidance on firms' earnings. They reported that big firms that engage in manipulations of earnings do not necessarily be as a result of tax avoidance.

Eko (2013) worked on the income tax rate and earnings management of firms listed on the Indonesian stock exchange. The study investigated the impacts of the firm's tax savings on management behavior in determining firms' earnings using financial data manufacturing firms from 2003 to 2009. The study used regression analysis to analyzed the independent variables (tax saving, statutory tax rate, effective tax rate) on the dependent variables (performance model, modified Jones model). The result shows negative significant effect of tax savings on firms earning stating that management tends to accrue expenses earlier

whenever circumstances available to minimize tax which affects firms earning. In the same way, revenue may be recognized in later year in order to manage income and tax saving.

Li (2014) worked on tax-induced earnings management, auditor conservatism, and tax enforcement using Hong Kong firms. The study used tax savings, enforcement, effective tax rate, quality high on earning manipulation as measure to earning manipulation, while using regression analysis to analyze the independent on the dependent variables. The result shows negative significant effect of tax savings on earning manipulation, this means that firms subject to stricter tax enforcement report higher discretionary current accruals than their counterparts when they have incentives to manage earnings downward for current tax savings.

Kaworl and Kportorgbi (2014) worked on the effect of tax planning on firms' market performance using non-financial companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange over a twelve year. They adopted panel regression to analysis the effect of tax saving, sales growth, firm size, leverage and age on firm performance poxied as Tobin's q. Their result shows a significant position effect of tax saving and firm earnings meaning that firms' engage in intensive tax planning activities when tax authorities maintain low corporate income tax rates that have a neutral influence on performance of firms under the study.

Hu, Cao and Zheng, (2015) worked on the effects of aggressive tax planning on firms earnings of 202 firms listed on Chinese capital market from 2008 to 2010. The study used book-tax differences and deferred tax expense as proxy to tax aggressive planning while nonconforming earnings management as proxy for earning manipulation. They used regression analysis to analyse the independent variables on the dependent variable. The result shows negative significant effect of aggressive tax planning on earnings manipulation indicating that firms has motivations to some aggressive tax planning strategies to reduce tax liability which affect the quality of earning.

Ingrid, (2017) worked on the effect of book-tax gap and corporate governance disclosure on the quality of earnings using accounting conservatism as moderating variables using listed companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2014. The study used book-tax gap, operating cash flow, and firms' growth as independent variables on earnings persistence as proxy for earnings manipulation, using multiple regression analysis to analyze the dependent and independent variables. The result shows significant effect on book tax gap on earnings manipulation indicating that firms with large book tax gap have lower earning persistence compared to firms with small book tax gap.

Rafay and Ajmal (2014) worked on the earnings management through deferred taxes recognized under IAS 12 using Pakistan firms. The study examines calculation of temporary difference under the IAS 12 and its impact of firm earnings valuation. They reported that studies indicate that temporary difference is a source of opportunistic earnings management, suggesting that because accounting principles gives managers more ability than tax authorities, while the decrease in tax paid through deferred tax liabilities is classified as tax avoidance. The study used temporary difference, abnormal operating earnings, deferred tax liabilities, earning quality to measure the dependent and independent variables, while using the regression analysis to analyze the impact of the variables. Their result shows a negatively effect of temporary tax difference on firms earnings meaning that Pakistani investors treat temporary tax difference negatively, penalizing companies that attempt to manage their earnings through the use of deferred taxes. It also shows that permanent tax difference have insignificant effect on firms' earnings, as permanent tax difference are due to different treatment between taxable and accounting income and expense. They reported that accrue in

permanent tax differences reflex in firm's accounting earnings, but they do not give rise to deferred tax assets or deferred tax liabilities.

Huang and Wang (2013) worked on the book-tax differences and earnings management for the banking industry using quoted firms in Taiwan. They concentrated on the banking industry because of the specific accrual models of accounting discretion in the loan loss provisions availability testing earnings management on how it is been effected by temporary tax differences. The variables are earnings manipulation, temporary tax differences, permanent tax differences, large positive book-tax differences, large negative book-tax differences, small book-tax differences while using regression analysis to analyze it. Their result shows that banks with large temporary book tax differences have discretionary loan loss provisions that are greater than banks with small temporary book-tax differences. The paper also finds that large temporary book-tax differences have significant negative effects on firms' earnings of the sample than those with small temporary book-tax differences while it reported no significant effects of permanent book-tax differences on firms' earnings.

Waluyo (2016) worked on the relationship between book-tax gap and earnings growth using Indonesian manufacturing firms within the period of 2010 to 2014. The study used permanent tax differences and temporary tax differences to capture tax avoidance of Indonesian firms while changes in pretax income and changes in net income were used to measure firms earnings. The study used size of firm, return on asset, operating cash flows and accrual income as control variables while using regression analysis to analyze the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The results show that permanent tax difference has a positive significant effect on firms' earnings while temporary tax difference has negative and significant effect on firms earning. He reported that firms with large temporary tax difference tend to have earnings that are not persistent.

Filho, Martinez and Anunciação (2013) worked on the analysis of the relationship between the components of book tax differences and annual variations in earnings and tax expenses using 130 companies listed firms on Brazilian stock exchange from 2004 to 2011. They used temporary tax differences, permanent tax differences, return on asset, ratio of earnings to stock price as independent variables while earnings management as dependent variable. The study used abnormal working capital accruals as a metric to infer the existence of earnings manipulation, to see whether this interferes in the relation of permanent tax differences or temporary tax differences with variations in pretax earnings and income tax expenses using regression analysis to analyze the variables. Their result shows a negative significant effect of temporary tax differences on firms' earnings while positive significant effect of permanent tax differences on firms earnings. They summarized their result that changes on temporary tax differences on future pretax earnings growth and permanent tax difference on future tax expense is useful for investors and analyst on tax avoidance effect on earnings manipulation.

Satyawati and Palupi (2017) worked on the influence of book tax differences on correlation of current earnings, accruals, and cash flows to future earnings using 147 registered firms listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange` from 2007 to 2011. They study used pre-tax book income, large negative temporary tax differences, large positive temporary tax differences, earnings before tax of the current period to measure the independent and dependent variables while using regression analysis to analyze the effects between the variables. Their result shows that large negative temporary tax differences are insignificant and do not affect the accounting earnings which means that firms with large negative temporary tax differences may not be

able to realize their future earnings. Secondly, that large temporary tax differences have positively significant effect on firms earning, meaning that firms with large positive temporary tax differences will persist to low tax returns due to their accrual, which affect their firms' earnings.

In summary, Salihu et al (2013), Dyeng et al (2010), Armstrong, Blouin and Lariker (2012) concentrated on effective tax rate without capturing the effects of temporary and permanent different of tax aggressiveness. Desai and Dharmapala (2006) argued that tax avoidance may not necessarily benefit stockholders and earnings. Hope. Ma and Thomas (2012), Richardson (2012), Chen and Chu (2005), Adhikari, Derashid and Zabg (2005) reported positive effects of tax avoidance on firms earnings while Ayres et al (2009), Hanlon and Slemord (2008) reported negative effects of tax avoidance on firms earnings. Ratay and Ajmal (2014) are of the view that temporary difference of tax shelter is a source of opportunistic earning management, saying that accounting principles gives managers more ability than tax authorities while Marques, Costa and Silva (2015) captured the usefulness of tax book gap on one measure of earnings quality (earnings per share). Huang and Wang (2013), Romanus (2007), Raedy, Seidman and Shackelford (2010), Blaylock, Shevlin and Wilson (2010) used modified Jones model to capture discretionary accruals while Warsharsky (2012) brought in earning manipulation model by Beneish of 5 and 8 scores as analytical tools on earnings manipulation. Most of these prior studies were done in developed countries such as United States and European countries, as well as in emerging economy as Indonesia, Ghana, and others.

3.0 Data and Model

The study engages a panel data by obtaining financial information covering selected quoted companies from 2009 to 2016. Data were obtained from the annual reports of the firms. The selection of the variables (regress and regressor) is primarily guided by the results of the previous empirical studies and the available data. Our population are 165 firms ranging from agriculture, conglomerate, construction/real estate, consumer goods, health care, information communication technology (ICT), industrial goods, natural resources, oil and gas, services and financial services. (Nigeria Stock Exchange 2017). While the sample size are of 116 quoted companies covering the whole sectors excluding financial services such as banking, insurance and mortgage sectors, due to the nature of their financial reporting system.

3.1 Model Specification and Measurement of Variables

In specifying our panel regression model of the effects corporate tax avoidance and earnings management on earnings manipulation, the indicator of earnings manipulation is the Beneish's earnings manipulation model (Benish~e); Modified Jones earnings management model is the proxy for earnings management (Modifi~l); cash effective tax rate (CashETR), long term effective tax rate (Lngter~R); tax saving (Taxesav~s); book tax gap (Bookta~p); temporary difference (Tempor~f) and permanent different (Perman~f) captures tax avoidance; firm size (Totala~s) and Total Revenue (TotalR~s) is included as a control variables. Lastly, interaction terms of cash effective tax rate and earnings management (CashETR*Modifi~l) and tax saving and earnings management (Taxesav~s*Modifi~l) are included to address the study questions. Also included in the model are cross-section (selected trading quoted companies) and years (2009 – 2016) in the panel regressions. The variables are sourced from Osiri data base.

In the light of the above, we measure earnings manipulation for the study to be based on the method used by Marail and Pavlović (2014), Warshavsky (2012), Kamarudin, and Ismail (2014), Healy (1985),

DeAngelo (1986) and Jones (1991), Dechow et al. (1995), Hermanns, (2006), Francis, LaFond, Olsson, and Schipper, (2004), Aboody, Hughes, and Liu, (2005), Myers, Myers, and Omer, (2003), Lyimo (2014), Perotti & Wagenhofer (2011). Scholars have widely employed earnings management as a proxy for earnings manipulation, particularly in valuing publicly traded companies.

3.2. Summary statistics and correlation analysis

Table 1 from appendix one shows the mean (average) for each of the variable, their maximum values, minimum values and standard deviation. With the emphasis on the indicators of interest, the average Beneish's is 3.23 high earnings manipulation of the quoted firms. On CashETR, the average proportion of accounting income payable is 27%, while on the long run (Lngter~R) is 22%. The maximum Booktaxp was N219million leading to N34.2billion on Temporary accumulated due to accrual method of earnings manipulation by quoted firms. The quoted firms' size is N2.3billion with a total revenue of N649million within the period.

Table 1 Summary statistics.

Variabls	Mean	Min	Max	Std. Dev
Beneish's	3.23e+12	-3.23e+14	7.96e+14	4.93e+13
Modifi~l	.3288148	-7.289997	2.3567	.5819565
CashETR	.2704482	-9.883898	41.83956	1.894761
Lngter~R	.2283744	-13.32587	54.8176	2.270622
Taxsav~s	.1566388	-21.92755	91.1839	3.358013
Booktaxp	911909.8	-2.23e+07	2.19e+08	1.19e+07
Tempor~f	7.79e+07	-4.55e+08	3.42e+10	1.55e+09
Perman~f	-6.86e+07	-3.40e+10	4.55e+08	1.45e+09
Totala~s	4.22e+07	0	2.30e+09	1.45e+08
TotalR~s	3.03e+07	0	6.49e+08	6.87e+07

Notes: For example: 7.79e+07= 77,900,000; Beneish's: Beneish's MScore, Modifi~l: Modified Jones Model, CashETR: cash effective tax rate, Lngter~R: long-term cash effective tax rate, Taxsav~s: tax savings, Booktaxp: = book tax gap, Tempor~f: = temporary difference, Perman~f: permanent difference, Totala~s: Firm Size, TotalR~s: Total Revenue. Source: Authors' Computations.

Table 2 details the pairwise correlation, which measures the relative association among the regressors and dependent variables. All the variables have statistically significant relationships with the dependent variable. On the regressors, all the variables having statistically significant association with Modifi~l except for taxsav~s and totala~s. Totala~s does not have statistically significant association with tempor~f, perman~f, totala~s and totalr~s. Tempor~f does not have statistically significant association with perman~f, totala~s and totalr~s, while perman~f does not have statistically significant association

with totala~s and totalr~s. A cursory look at Table 2 indicates no presence of multicollinearity among the covariates as all correlation statistics are below 0.90.

Table 2 Correlation Matrix

Variables	Benish~e	Modifi~l	CashETR	Lngter~R	Taxsav~s	Bookta~p	Tempor~f	Perman~f	Totala~s	TotalR~s
Benish~e	1.0000									
Modifi~l	0.0332***	1.0000								
CashETR	-0.0026**	-0.1927	1.0000							
Lngter~R	0.0157**	-0.0104**	0.0413***	1.0000						
Taxsav~s	0.0072**	0.1365	-0.5557	-0.0752***	1.0000					
Bookta~p	-0.0061**	0.0763***	-0.0387***	-0.0875***	0.0662***	1.0000				
Tempor~f	-0.0037**	0.0331***	-0.0248***	0.0079**	0.0324 ***	0.7074	1.0000			
Perman~f	0.0037**	-0.0327***	0.0247 ***	-0.0074**	-0.0321***	-0.7057	-1.0000	1.0000		
Totala~s	0.0269***	0.1609	-0.0470***	-0.0606***	0.0360***	0.5809	0.3725	-0.3700	1.0000	
TotalR~s	0.0910***	0.1047***	-0.0368 ***	-0.0098**	-0.0285***	0.3765	0.2681	-0.2665	0.8580	1.0000

Notes: Notes: *** and ** represent statistical significance at the 0.1% and 1% levels, respectively. Benish~e: Beneish's MScore, Modifi~l: Modified Jones Model, CashETR: cash effective tax rate, Lngter~R: long-term cash effective tax rate, Taxsav~s: tax savings, Bookta~p: = book tax gap, Tempor~f: = temporary difference, Perman~f: permanent difference, Totala~s: Firm Size, TotalR~s: Total Revenue

Source: Authors' Computations.

3.3 Estimating Models

In exploring the empirical association between earnings manipulation and various explanatory variables of this study, linear dynamic panel models were set out. In this respect, three (3) models were specified. In order to control for exogenous variables, the first model captured conventional determinants of earnings manipulation. The selection of the control variables were largely influenced by prior studies. The first dynamic panel model, which represents the baseline model of this study, demonstrates that earnings manipulation is the function of six conventional factors. The baseline model is incorporated in the analysis in order to estimate the effect of the six conventional factors on earnings manipulation.

The second dynamic panel model was derived by expanding the baseline model (1) to include the control variables. This expanded model was re-estimated to determine whether firms size and firms revenue promotes earnings manipulations for sample quoted companies. The model was further extended by inserting earnings management as a moderating variable(s) to obtain the third dynamic panel model. The third model was used to estimate the effect of the interaction of tax avoidance and earnings management on earnings manipulations

$$\text{Benish}\sim e_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{CashETR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Lngter}\sim R_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Taxsav}\sim s_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Bookta}\sim p_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Tempor}\sim f_{it} + \beta_6 \text{Perman}\sim f_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{equ (1)}$$

$$\text{Benish}\sim e_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{CashETR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Lngter}\sim R_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Taxsav}\sim s_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Bookta}\sim p_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Tempor}\sim f_{it} + \beta_6 \text{Perman}\sim f_{it} + \beta_7 \text{Totala}\sim s_{it} + \beta_8 \text{TotalR}\sim s_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{equ (2)}$$

$$\text{Benish}\sim e_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_1 \text{CashETR}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Lngter}\sim R_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Taxsav}\sim s_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Bookta}\sim p_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Tempor}\sim f_{it} + \beta_6 \text{Perman}\sim f_{it} + \beta_7 \text{Totala}\sim s_{it} + \beta_8 \text{TotalR}\sim s_{it} + \beta_9 \text{Modifi}\sim l_{it} + \beta_{10} (\text{CashETR} * \text{Modifi}\sim l)_{it} + \beta_{11} (\text{Taxsav}\sim s * \text{Modifi}\sim l)_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{equ (3)}$$

Where **Benish~e** denotes Beneish's M-Score earnings manipulation model. M-Score is a quantitative forensic indexing method developed to assist in detecting whether a company has manipulated its earnings used by Marai and Pavlović (2014), Warshavsky (2012). The model uses eight financial variables viewed as being indicators of firms prone to financial statement manipulation which are changes in accounts receivable (DSRI), deteriorating gross margins (GMI), decreasing asset quality (AQI), sales growth (SGI), depreciation index (DEPI), Sales, General and Administrative (SGAI), Total Accruals to Total Assets (TATA), and leverage index (LVGI). $M = -4.84 + 0.92(\text{DSRI}) + 0.528(\text{GMI}) + 0.404(\text{AQI}) + 0.892(\text{SGI}) + 0.115(\text{DEPI}) - 0.172(\text{SGAI}) + 4.679(\text{TATA}) - 0.327(\text{LVGI})$. A score of greater than -2.22 (i.e., less of a negative) is an indication that the firm's financial statements may have been manipulated. Firms with higher Beneish scores are more likely to be manipulators while $\text{Benish}\sim e_{it-1}$ stands for first lagged $\text{Benish}\sim e$. **CashETR** which represents cash effective tax rate measured as Total tax expenses divided by the income before tax as done in some previous studies Salihu et al., (2013), Chen et al. (2010) Dyreng et al., (2010). The variable **Lngter~R** is long-term cash effective tax rate measured as total tax expenses divided by the income before tax. Uses the tax information for multiple years Chen et al. (2010); Dyreng et al. (2010); Minnick & Noga (2010); Kim, Li & Zhang (2011); Salihu et al., (2013); Hanlon & Heitzman, 2010:140 in Salihu et al., 2013. **Taxsav~s** is tax savings used as proxied of difference between the statutory tax rate and the effective tax rate ($\text{TaxSav} = 30\% - \text{ETR}$) Ilaboya, Izevbekhai and Ohiokha (2016), Ftouhi, Ayed and Zemzem, 2010; Kawor and Kportorgbi 2014, Lisowsky, Lennox and Pittman 2013, Atwood and Reynolds 2008. While **Bookta~p** denotes book tax gap measured as differences between income reported on financial statements and income reported on tax returns. $\text{BTG} = \text{EBIT} - \text{TI}$. Taxable income is calculated as current tax expense divided by corporate statutory rate (30%) Seidman, (2008); Talisman (1999); Mills, Newberry and Trautman (2002); Desai (2003); Waluyo (2016); Plesko, 2004 in Satyawati and Palupi 2017. **Tempor~f** represents the temporary difference measured by the deferred tax expense divided by the corporate statutory rate (deferred tax / 30%) while the variable **Perman~f** which is permanent difference is measured by book tax gap less temporary tax differences ($\text{BTG} - \text{TemDiff}$) Seidman, (2008). **Totala~s**: Firm Size. **TotalR~s**: Total Revenue. **Modifi~l** = Modified Jones model. We proxy earnings management with modified Jones model. The model estimates firms' abnormal accruals (discretionary) based on certain economic and accounting fundamentals

using time series regression used by Dechow, Ge, and Schrand, (2010), Dechow, and Dichev (2002). $\mu_t = DA_t = \{TA_t\} - \{(\beta_{0i} (1/T_{t-1}) + \beta_{1i}(\Delta REV_t - \Delta REC_t) + \beta_{2i} (PPE_t))\}$ Where DA_t = Discretionary accruals in year t, TA_t = Actual total accruals from financial statement data = $\{\Delta \text{Current assets} - \Delta \text{cash} - \Delta \text{current liabilities} - \Delta \text{Current maturities of long-term debt} - \Delta \text{Income taxes payable} - \text{Depreciation and amortization expenses}\}$, ΔREV_t is the change in revenues from last year to this year, ΔREC_t is the change in receivables from last year to this year, PPE_t is the book value of property, plant and equipment. The model measure of the firm's operations before managers' manipulations. It is expected that total accruals, which includes changes in accounts receivables, rely on the extent of changes in revenue, as revenues are to control for firms economic environment, the gross property, plant and equipment control for the portion of total accruals related to non-discretionary depreciation expense. The prediction error in the model, μ_t measures the level of discretionary accruals. The coefficient of β_{10} and β_{11} which was obtained from moderating product of tax avoidance and modified Jones model represents the interaction between the variables while the subscript i represents companies while t denotes the time. $i = 1 \dots 115$ and $t = 2009 \dots 2016$.

3.4 Estimation Technique

The estimation of the dynamic panel models of this study was performed by applying Generalised Method of Moment (GMM) technique. The GMM estimator was developed by the contributions of Arellano and Bond (1991), Arellano and Bover (1995) as well as Blundell and Bond (1998). Dynamic panel models can be applied using either the „Difference“ GMM technique or „System“ GMM technique. At the same time, the dynamic model is the Arellano and Bond (1991) one-step difference generalized method of moments (difference-GMM) estimator technique which corrects for endogeneity, cross-sectional dependence, serial correlation and heteroscedasticity by including instruments that are uncorrelated with the regressors in the underlying routine during estimation. One-step System GMM technique was used in this study, the choice of applying of GMM estimator was influenced by two factors. First, some researchers have noted that the past earnings of a firm is capable of influencing the current earnings. In order to capture the influence of past earnings on the current earnings of sample firms, lagged earnings manipulation model was incorporated into models of this study. It is on this ground that GMM estimator was considered suitable for this study. As stated in Piper (2014), GMM is designed to include a lag of the dependent variable on the right-hand side of the regression equation. Second, GMM estimator was used to address the problem of heteroskedaticity which OLS exhibited when it was initially applied on the data of the study. This was done in consonance with the suggestions of Wooldridge (2001) that GMM estimators is more efficient than OLS in the presence of heteroskedaticity.

4. Results and Discussions

This section presents empirical findings which fill essential gaps in the tax avoidance and earnings management on Nigeria firms by showcasing findings on whether cash tax rate individually drives earnings and earnings management and/or if its interaction with tax savings enhances or alters its impact on earnings manipulation. Estimations begin with conventional determinants of earnings manipulation, column [1] OLS, column [2] composite OLS robustness regression. The GMM results grouped into 'main' and 'robustness', column [3] relate to the earnings management (Modifi~1) as a moderating variable. Their corresponding with firms size (Totala~s) and firms revenue (TotalR~s) as an additional control variables are reflected in column [4]. Consequently, column [5] was extended to include earnings management (Modifi~1) and its interaction with tax avoidance (CashETR and Taxsav~s) to obtain model 3. Columns [6] and [7] reflected year dummies while [7] reflected their corresponding robustness checks.

Table 3. One-step difference GMM results.

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	GMM Regressions						Robustness Checks
	Benish~e [1]	Benish~e [2]	Benish~e [3]	Benish~e [4]	Benish~e [5]	Benish~e [6]	Benish~e [7]
Constant	1.23 (0.87)	1.23 (0.76)	1.47 (0.96)	8.99 (0.38)	15.58 (1.35)	30.03 (1.35)	30.03 (3.14)*
Benish~e_1			0.00 (0.15)	0.00 (0.05)	-5.74 (-0.31)	5.24 (0.65)	5.24 (2.61)*
CashETR	2.45 (0.03)	2.45 (0.07)	-3.42 (-0.70)	-3.43 (-0.69)	-9.84 (-1.18)	-13.41 (-0.88)	-13.41 (-2.75)*
Lngrter~R	2.80 (0.01)	2.80 (0.06)	1.19 (0.50)	1.13 (0.46)	0.42 (0.23)	0.05 (0.02)	0.05 (0.05)
Taxsav~s	2.95 (0.13)	2.95 (0.15)	-1.95 (-1.11)	-1.96 (-1.10)	-1.26 (-0.23)	-13.28 (-1.04)	-13.28 (-2.20)**
Bookta~p	-927.78 (-0.08)	-927.78 (-1.06)	-1431.41 (-0.19)	-1123.48 (-0.14)	8.97 (0.26)	1.51 (0.24)	1.51 (0.75)
Tempor~f	199.84 (0.02)	199.84 (0.42)	-677.30 (-0.12)	-876.07 (-0.15)	-1.38 (-0.27)	-3.73 (-0.43)	-3.73 (-1.24)
Perman~f	198.84 (0.02)	198.84 (0.42)	-680.03 (-0.12)	-875 (-0.15)	5.37 (0.10)	-3.39 (-0.37)	-3.39 (-1.80)**
Totala~s				458.40 (0.13)	3.75 (0.30)	1.20 (0.51)	1.20 (2.80)*
TotalR~s				444.63 (0.09)	-6.32 (-0.51)	-9.95 (-0.51)	-9.95 (-2.74)*
Modifi~l			-7.45 (-2.51)*	-7.45 (-2.49)	-12.86 (-1.68)***	-20.35 (-1.39)	-20.35 (-3.56)*
CashETR* Modifi~l					3.13 (1.09)	4.34 (0.81)	4.34 (2.62)*
Taxsav~s*Modifi~l					0.46 (0.21)	4.23 (0.82)	4.23 (2.22)**
Time Dummies	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
No of Obs.	918	918	918	918	918	918	918
R-Squared	0.0001	0.0001					
Adj-R-Squared	-0.021						
F-Statistic	0.00 (1.00)	0.24 (0.96)					
Instruments/Group			36/51	38/51	23/15	23/15	23/15
Wald test/ P-value			7.89	7.80	9.02	6.52	1.71*

Notes: *, **, *** are statistical significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively; t-statistics in () are based on White heteroscedasticity-consistent std. errors
Source: Authors' Computations.

The Generalised Method of Moment (GMM) results in Table 3, the lag Benish~e is positively associated with Benish~e at 1% significance level. The results also provide evidence that the cash effective tax rate (CashETR) in Nigeria exert negative significant impact on earnings manipulation. This result which generally agrees with the previous findings in the literature (Frank, Lynch and Rego, 2009; Salihu et al., 2013; Demeré, Lisowsky, Li, and Snyder, 2017, Osegbue, and Nwoye, 2021) demonstrates the fact that cash effective tax rate serves as an indicator to financial reporting quality on both reducing and increasing earning quality. The result regarding to the impact of tax savings (Taxesav~s) on earnings manipulation is negative and statistically significant in model. This result is similar to the once reported in Eko (2013); Brad, Sharon and Sonja (2010); Li (2014) that management tends to accrue expenses earlier whenever circumstances available to minimize tax which affects earning quality. On permanent difference (Perman~f), the coefficient is negatively statistically significant at 10%, the sign of the coefficient aligns with the outcomes of some studies that permanent tax difference are due to different treatment between taxable and accounting income and expense but they do not give rise to deferred tax assets or deferred tax liabilities. It does not change taxable income and tax relative to book income. However, it may either strengthen or weaken the information in taxable income less reported earnings, depending on their variability and correlations. (Rafay and Ajmal, 2014; Lev and Nissim, 2004).

The impact of Totala~s and TotalR~s on earnings manipulation is asymmetric. While both exert statistically significant effects on earnings manipulation at the 1% level. But the impact on earnings manipulation is positive and statistically significant for firms size (Totala~s) while it is negative and statistically significant for firms revenue (TotalR~s). Exhibiting an elastic relationship, a percentage change in firms' size leads to increase in earnings manipulation, while a percentage change in firms' revenue leads to decrease in earnings manipulation. The results indicate that modified jones model (Modifi~l) also negatively and significantly moderate the relationship between earnings management and earnings manipulation. These results prove that the efficient earnings management will reduce earnings manipulation. Meanwhile, the interaction of modified jones model (Modifi~l) as well as cash effective tax (CashETR) and tax savings (Taxesav~s) with tax avoidance exerts positive and significant effects on earnings manipulation. This implies that change in cash effective tax and tax savings leads to increase in earnings manipulation. Lastly, while controlling for year dummies, the goodness-of-fit of the models shows that the GMM results indicates that Wald test (1.71*) is statistically appropriate to predict earnings manipulation to the sampled firms; there is no evidence of second-order serial correlation given the indicated pvalues while the null hypothesis of instruments validity cannot be rejected at the 1% significance level. Hence, the results obtained from these augmented regressions can be used for inferences.

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Implications

This study which is primarily motivated by the need to have better understanding of how the host tax avoidance influences earnings manipulation in presence of earnings management, investigates the theoretical relationship between tax avoidance and earnings manipulation in 116 quoted companies in Nigeria using unbalanced data covering 2009 -2016. The results from dynamic difference GMM analysis reveal a number of interesting new evidence which would undoubtedly bridge knowledge gap in the literature. In broader terms, this paper addresses two research questions among which is whether tax avoidance significantly impacts earnings manipulation and if the adoption of earnings management influences the impact of earnings manipulation? Specifically, this study concludes that (1) tax avoidance

significantly serves as an indicator to financial reporting quality on both reducing and increasing earnings manipulation; (2) the positive interaction of tax avoidance and earnings management implies that earnings management favourably moderates the connection between tax avoidance and earnings manipulation.

The findings of this study give rise to some important implications that worth noting by policy makers in Nigeria. First, empirical evidence that suggests negative significant impact of cash effective tax rate (CashETR), tax savings (Taxsav~s) and permanent difference (Perman~f) on earnings manipulation; goes to demonstrate that the level of earnings manipulation of sampled firms in Nigeria driven by the extent of the cash effective tax rate, tax savings and permanent difference, which reflects the tax avoidance while holding other factors constant. Consequently, cash effective tax rate serves as an indicator to financial reporting quality on both reducing and increasing earning quality.

Secondly, the evidence showing that earnings management exerts positive and significant moderating impact on the relationship between tax avoidance and earnings manipulation in Nigeria. This suggests that the tax avoidance alone is not enough to enhance earnings manipulation but it must be accompanied by earnings management. Therefore, policy makers (tax authorities) in Nigeria must take into consideration the interconnectedness between earnings management and tax avoidance in formulating strategies towards earnings manipulation as this would have greater impact than strategy that focused on tax avoidance alone. In this regard, we recommend that various indicators of earnings management should be further strengthened particularly in respect accrual expenses as its application in taxation so as to improve the earnings management in Nigeria.

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Appendix 1

Table A1. List of years

year	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
2009	113	12.31	12.31
2010	115	12.53	24.84
2011	115	12.53	37.36
2012	115	12.53	49.89
2013	115	12.53	62.42
2014	115	12.53	74.95
2015	115	12.53	87.47
2016	115	12.53	100.00
Total	918	100.00	

Table A2. List of sectors

industry	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
Agriculture	24	2.61	2.61
Conglomerate	40	4.36	6.97
Construction/Real estate	64	6.97	13.94
Consumer goods	184	20.04	33.99
Healthcare	80	8.71	42.70
ICT	56	6.10	48.80
Industrial goods	135	14.71	63.51
Natural resources	24	2.61	66.12
Oil and gas	104	11.33	77.45
Services	207	22.55	100.00
Total	918	100.00	

